

INSPIRATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN OTHER COUNTRIES

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Annotation. *This topic explores successful sustainable development initiatives from various countries, serving as inspiration for others. It delves into case studies, best practices, and innovative approaches in areas such as economic growth, social progress, and environmental protection. By highlighting these examples, the annotation aims to showcase how international collaboration and knowledge exchange can foster sustainable development efforts worldwide.*

Keywords: “World Natural Resources Conservation Program”, “Building a Sustainable Development Society”.

Sustainable development first appeared in the International Union for Conservation of Nature’s “World Natural Resources Conservation Program” in 1980: “It is necessary to study the basic relationships between nature, society, ecology, economy and the process of utilizing natural resources to ensure global sustainability. Sustainable development”. In 1981, Lester R. Brown published “Building a Sustainable Development Society”, proposing to achieve sustainable development by controlling population growth, protecting the resource base and developing renewable energy. In 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development published the report “Our Common Future”, which systematically elaborated on the idea of sustainable development and defined sustainable development as: “It is necessary to study the basic relationships between nature, society, ecology, economy and the process of utilizing natural resources to ensure global sustainable development”. In June 1992, the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro adopted the “Rio Declaration on Environment and Development”, “Agenda 21” and other documents with sustainable development as the core.

In 1989, the “United Nations Conference on Environment and Development” (UNEP) adopted the “Statement on Sustainable Development” specifically for the definition and strategy of “sustainable development”. It believed that the definition and strategy of sustainable development mainly include four aspects: (1) Towards national and international equality; (2) To have a supportive international economic environment; (3) To maintain, rationally use and enhance the natural resource base; (4) To incorporate environmental concerns and considerations into development plans and policies.

In short, sustainable development is a development based on the mutual coordination and common development of society, economy, population, resources and environment. Its purpose is to relatively meet the needs of the present generation without jeopardizing the development of future generations.

Sustainable development focuses on the coordinated “development” of society, economy, culture, resources, environment, life and other aspects, and requires the changes in the vector composed of various indicators in these aspects to show a monotonic increase (strong sustainable development).

Many countries in the world adhere to sustainable development strategies, and these successful experiences can help Uzbekistan.

France is one of the main sponsors of the European Union and a modern market economy country with a developed economy. When formulating economic policies, the French government places sustainable development strategy in a very important position, striving to both promote economic development and achieve environmental protection, and has done a lot of work to this end.

① Establishing and improving systems and improving institutional settings: France has always attached great importance to ensuring the effective implementation of policy measures through the use of legislative means. As early as 1960, France passed the National Parks Law and the Water Law in 1964, which included a financial incentive constraint mechanism based on the principle of “polluter pays”. France approved the National Environmental Plan at the end of 1990, which led to the first large-scale reform of the environmental management sector. The period 1998-2001 was a critical period for the development of France’s low-carbon economy. The government adopted new behavioral measures and strengthened legislation, especially the formulation of laws on territorial remediation and its long-term development direction (1999) and the adoption of environmental regulations (2000). Since 2002, France has focused environmental protection on sustainable development and formulated a national environmental protection strategy.

② Actively study and introduce relevant fiscal and taxation policies: France strongly supports resource conservation and environmental protection through taxation, government procurement, fiscal expenditure and other tools. Overall, the fiscal and taxation policies introduced by France are very targeted, and there is much to learn from in terms of details. First, France’s fiscal and taxation policies have clear support targets and standards. The objects of government support in energy conservation include, first, research, development and production units of energy-saving technologies and equipment, such as support for research projects and demonstration projects. The second is to provide financial subsidies to companies or consumers who purchase energy-saving equipment or technology. If companies or consumers purchase catalog products published by the government, they will receive a subsidy of 15%-20% of the equipment price. The third is social intermediary organizations that implement energy-saving publicity and education. More than 500 “energy-saving technology promotion organizations” in France bid for energy-saving publicity and technology promotion projects to the governments of the EU and its member states every year. The winning bidder will receive financial support from the government. Secondly, France pays targeted attention to key areas of energy conservation and environmental protection. The first is to adopt policies and measures to encourage energy conservation in the construction sector. For existing houses, tax incentives (refund of personal income tax) are mainly provided for the purchase of energy-saving equipment. The second is to introduce corresponding policies in the field of transportation energy conservation. The first is to use administrative means to limit vehicle speeds and implement energy-saving certification for new transportation vehicles. Secondly, we should actively adopt financial incentives and use tax rebate policies to encourage the use of clean energy. Finally, a special purchase tax is levied on high-consumption cars, and company cars pay an environmental tax.

Japan has also faced environmental pollution problems caused by the industrialization process. However, due to the earlier industrialization, the governance and protection of the ecological environment were also implemented earlier, forming a set of effective environmental protection measures, which have certain reference significance for other countries or regions to deal with environmental issues.

① Improve the environmental legal system and clarify government responsibilities: The “Basic Environmental Law” is the main legal basis for the Japanese government to carry out environmental governance. This law is based on the 1967 “Basic Law on Pollution Countermeasures”. After a thorough revision of the “Basic Law on Pollution Countermeasures” in 1970, it was officially promulgated in 1993, which lasted 26 years. Japan’s “Basic Environmental Law” has three basic concepts: “Establishing a society with low environmental load and sustainable development”, “enjoying and inheriting the benefits of the environment” and “actively promoting global environmental protection within the international coordination framework”. In terms of establishing environmental standards, relevant departments of the central government should target environmental conditions involving pollution, and from the perspective of protecting people’s health and maintaining the living environment, organize medical experts in relevant fields to determine various standards through consultation and clarify the policy objectives of environmental protection. In terms of plan formulation, it mainly includes two categories: “Basic Environmental Plan” and “Pollution Prevention Plan”. In terms of dispute resolution, on the one hand, it clearly stipulates the government’s specific support for disputes between residents who are harmed by environmental pollution and emitters. On the other hand, local governments have relevant consultation windows and committees composed of experts carry out actual mediation work. Most of the actual costs incurred are borne by the government.

② Implement environmental education strategies to enhance the environmental awareness of various entities. Since the 1970s, the Japanese government has begun to actively promote pollution education, natural experience learning, etc. to enhance the environmental awareness of citizens and other social entities, and actively promote environmental education legislation. In the 1990s, the Japanese government began to promote and implement the practice of “Education for Sustainable Development (ESD)”. It was not until November 1993 that environmental education was officially written into law. Article 25 of the “Basic Environmental Law” clearly stipulates “promoting environmental education and other work”. In 2003, the Japanese government specially launched the “Environmental Education Promotion Act” to carry out education and learning activities to deepen environmental protection. On the basis of this law, in June 2011, the Japanese government introduced the “Environmental Education, etc. Promotion Law”.

③ Encourage public supervision and strengthen corporate social responsibility: The Japanese government encourages all types of entities in society, especially the media, to participate in environmental protection work. In order to promote the coordination of corporate production and ecological environmental protection, the Japanese government has also successively introduced subordinate laws to the “Basic Environmental Law”, including the “Air Pollution Prevention and Control Law” to regulate corporate production activities. For example, formulating emission standards for production enterprises; providing administrative guidance to enterprises, guiding enterprises to independently improve environmental pollution problems that may arise during the production process, and conducting real-time monitoring of enterprise production activities.

④ Actively participate in and promote global environmental protection and improve international voice: The Japanese government attaches great importance to and participates in global environmental protection and actively promotes Japanese environmental protection experience and concepts to countries around the world. On the one hand, the Japanese government has participated in and formulated international environmental standards by actively participating

in international environment and development conferences held by international organizations such as the United Nations, which has significantly improved the Japanese government's international voice in the field of global environmental protection issues. On the other hand, the Japanese government also actively carries out environmental diplomacy activities by strengthening cooperation with other countries in the field of environmental protection, which is conducive to the promotion of Japan's domestic environmental protection experience and the overseas business expansion of environmental protection-related enterprises.

China's measures are more modest. Sustainable development strategy has become a concept with a very wide range of applications in China today. It is not only used in economic, social, environmental and other aspects, but also often used in education, life, art and other aspects.

① Firstly, transforming the economic development model and strategically adjusting the economic structure are major decisions to promote sustainable economic development. It is not only necessary to adjust the demand structure, but also to base national economic growth more on the basis of expanding domestic demand.

② Secondly, China regards the establishment of a resource-saving and environment-friendly society as an important focus in promoting sustainable development, and promotes production methods that are conducive to resource conservation and environmental protection in all systems of the entire society.

③ China regards ensuring and improving people's livelihood as a core requirement for sustainable development. Sustainable development actually talks about human equality and basic rights. The core of all issues of sustainable development is the all-round development of human beings.

From the implementation experience of the above countries, we found that the implementation of sustainable development strategy is conducive to promoting the unity of ecological benefits, economic benefits and social benefits, and is also conducive to promoting the transformation of economic growth mode from extensive to intensive, so that economic development and population, Resources and environment are coordinated. Sustainable development is conducive to the stability and healthy development of the national economy and improves people's living standards and quality.

Observing the specific implementation measures of the above countries, we can make some suggestions for Uzbekistan's sustainable development strategy:

① Don't follow the path of "pollution first, treatment later". We need to strike a balance between environmental protection and high-quality development. Generally speaking, developed countries are more inclined to implement stricter environmental protection standards globally, while developing countries, based on the needs of development, do not want their own industrialization processes to be bound by environmental protection policies. For Uzbekistan, development is still the top priority. In terms of the choice of development mode, it should transform from extensive growth with high input and high energy consumption to high-quality development with low input and high output.

② The rule of law is the foundation of environmental governance. Actively promote the legalization of environmental governance methods and policies. The government should continuously improve the environmental protection legal system based on actual development needs, while clarifying the responsibilities and obligations of various social entities such as

governments, residents, and enterprises, and bringing ecological and environmental governance into the orbit of the rule of law.

③ Carry out environmental education work. At the beginning of environmental governance, the government should always pay attention to the cultivation, publicity and education of environmental awareness of citizens and other social entities. People should be made more aware of environmental protection, especially in the classification of household waste and their sense of independent responsibility for protecting the surrounding environment. This can effectively reduce the government's public cost of environmental management.

④ Fiscal and taxation policies are the most effective tool for the government to directly guide the behavior of market entities. Uzbekistan's fiscal and taxation policies and measures should be deeply rooted in reality, cover all levels of the economy and society, and actively play their due role. The government should improve the resource tax system, expand the scope of collection, improve the basis for tax calculation, increase the amount of resource tax on scarce resources, highly polluting and high energy-consuming minerals, and implement preferential tax policies for imported resource products.

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